

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FUNCTIONALIZED NANOTUBE BUCKYPAPER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Buckypapers of long SWNTs and MWNTs were functionalized using m-Chloroperoxybenzoic acid (m-CPBA). After functionalization, epoxide groups were introduced on the sidewalls, which can react with the curing agent of epoxy resin to cross-link with the epoxy resin matrix and form covalent bonding to improve interfacial bonding and load transfer between the nanotubes and the matrix. The tensile test results show that the tensile strength and modulus of the functionalized MWNT BP composites noticeably improved. The tensile modulus of the functionalized SWNT BP composites increased, but its tensile strength was decreased due to possible large property degradation of the functionalized SWNTs. The improvement of interfacial bonding and loading transfer are evidenced by mechanical property improvements, nanotube breaks, good interfacial bonding at the fracture surfaces, and failure mode changes of the resultant composites. The functionalized MWNT BP composites show high mechanical performance, comparable to carbon fiber fabric composites for structural applications. The developed functionalization method and composite fabrication technique have the potential to scale up for industrial applications.

Keywords: Buckypaper, functionalized, high loading, composites

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes possess excellent mechanical properties, thermal and electric conductivity, and other exceptional and unique characteristics [1]. However, the mechanical properties of the resultant carbon nanotube composites in the literature are far below expectations [2]. Four main factors determine the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube composites [3]: 1) dispersion of nanotubes in composites, 2) interfacial bonding between the nanotube and matrix, 3) aspect ratio for load transfer, and 4) alignment of the nanotubes for optimizing mechanical properties.

Nanotube sheet or buckypapers, which are thin (5-25 μ m) films of nanotube networks, is a promising platform for fabricating high concentration and aligned nanotube-reinforced composites. Sheet-like buckypaper material is easy to handle and can be used in conventional composite manufacturing processes to fabricate nanocomposites. In buckypapers, nanotube network structures are pre-formed during buckypaper fabrication. Good dispersion, dense packing and alignment can be realized before

impregnating the buckypapers with resins, creating high-quality nanocomposites. Since the concept of buckypaper was first introduced by Dr. R.E. Smalley's group in 1998 [4], many researchers have investigated buckypaper or nanotube thin film/sheet [5-7] and its composite applications [8].

To realize high mechanical performance, good interfacial bonding between nanotubes and resin matrices is essential. Effectively grafting required chemical groups on the sidewalls of nanotubes is one of the effective methods to improve interfacial bonding [9]. Different reaction mechanisms can be utilized to graft functional groups on nanotube sidewalls, including halogenation, hydrogenation, cycloaddition, radical addition, electrophilic addition, addition of inorganic compounds and directly grafting polymer chains, etc. [10] Radical addition is one of the most effective methods. Wang, et al. successfully functionalized SWNTs using BPO (benzyl peroxide) and GMA (glycidyl methacrylate) through a radical reaction to graft epoxide groups [11]. The resulting nanocomposites showed a noticeable improvement in interfacial bonding and mechanical properties. Ogrin, et al. demonstrated the effectiveness of using m-CPBA to graft epoxide groups on SWNTs [12].

The aspect ratio of the nanotubes is an important factor affecting the mechanical properties of nanocomposites. Usually, the aspect ratio of nanotubes is lower than 1,000 in nanocomposites [13, 14]. However, recent commercially available millimeter-long carbon nanotubes have a large aspect ratio up to the order of 10,000-100,000 [15, 16]. A high aspect ratio of nanotubes can more effectively transfer the load to improve the mechanical properties of nanocomposites. Efforts of using long nanotubes for enhancing the mechanical performance of nanocomposites were also reported [17, 18].

In this research, the aligned long SWNT and MWNT sheet or buckypaper was functionalized to improve interfacial bonding with the epoxy matrix, and the buckypaper composites with high nanotube loading were fabricated using a prepreg process. The effects of functionalization on the mechanical properties of the resultant nanocomposites were investigated. Substantial mechanical property improvements of the resultant nanocomposites were demonstrated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Long MWNT and SWNT sheets or buckypapers were supplied by Nanocomp (Concord, NH). The length of the nanotubes is about 1mm [16]. Epon 862 epoxy and curing agent W (diethyltoluenediamines) were purchased from E.V. Rubber Inc. M-chloromethaneperoxybenzoic (m-CPBA) acid was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All raw materials were used as received.

Functionalization of buckypaper

m-CPBA was dissolved in dichloromethane or a benzene solvent, and the buckypaper was immersed in the solution for various times at room temperature (22-25°C) to conduct functionalization. The functionalized buckypapers were removed and washed

with alcohol at least three times. Finally, the treated BP was transferred to a vacuum oven for drying at 80°C for 2 hours. Type text here.

Fabrication of buckypaper composites

Epoxy resin Epon862 and curing agent W (ratio of Epon 862 epoxy to curing agent W was 100 to 26.4 by weight) were dissolved in acetone to develop an epoxy resin solution. Pristine and functionalized buckypapers were cut into samples of 55 mm by 27 mm. The buckypapers were then immersed in an epoxy resin solution for several minutes and removed to make buckypaper/epoxy prepregs. The prepregs were dried in a vacuum oven to allow the resin to become B-stage. To realize a high weight fraction of BP in the composites, the concentration of the epoxy resin solution used in the experiment was 15%-20%. The prepregs were stacked together and moved into a hot press to be cured at 177 °C for 2 hours.

Raman Spectrum Analysis

An inVia Raman Microscope (Renishaw Inc.) was used for Raman spectrum analysis. The major parameters were laser wavelength: 785nm, laser gate: 1200 l/mm, exposure time: 100s, and laser power level: 0.2%.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

A JEOL JSM-7401F Field Emission Scanning Microscope (JEOL USA, Inc.) was used. Samples for SEM experiments were sputter-coated for 60s at a current of 5mA.

Tensile Property Test

Composite samples were tested using a Shimadzu material testing machine (Kyoto, Japan). The experiments were conducted in accordance with ASTM D638-03.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanism of functionalizing carbon nanotubes by m-CPBA

Usually, the double bonds of alkenes are easy to oxidized using a strong oxidant, such as ozone, permanganate, peroxyacid, etc. Alkenes reacting with peroxyacid can result in the formation of an epoxide group [19], which is much preferred for making epoxy resin matrix-based composites. The chemical reactivity of the double bonds of unsaturated carbon atoms at the end caps and defective walls of the carbon nanotubes are almost the same as normal organic alkene molecules: their double bonds are easy to oxidize using a strong oxidant, or subject to an additional reaction with free radicals [20-22]. Hence, we can utilize peroxyacid, such as m-Chloroperoxybenzoic acid, to oxidize carbon nanotubes to directly graft much-needed epoxide groups at the caps and sidewalls of nanotubes. The advantages of this functionalization are that the reaction can occur at room temperature in an organic solvent, requiring less intensive reaction conditions, to

avoid a possible destroying the buckypaper structures. Figure 1 shows the proposed possible functionalization mechanism of nanotubes with m-CPBA acid. The m-CPBA easily forms an intramolecular hydrogen bond in an organic solvent, and the m-CPBA molecular is polarized at a high degree to result in the electrophilic oxygen atom “1” being able to attack a carbon atom on the nanotube, which is nucleophilic, to form a transition state – the “butterfly transition state.” In the transition state, the “O-O” bond is the weakest, and is usually the first broken forming the C-O with the carbon atom and forming a new “C=O.” The “H” atom is transferred to the “O” atom on the original C=O to simultaneously form a new “OH” group. So, the oxygen atom “1” is separated from m-CPBA to form an epoxide group with the nanotube.

Fig.1. Mechanism of functionalizing nanotube by m-CPBA.

Raman analysis

After functionalization, some sp² hybridized orbitals were changed to sp³ hybridized ones, which should lead to a noticeable increase of D band intensity and a reduction of G band intensity [23]. Figure 2 shows the intensity ratio of the D band and G band is totally reversed with the increase of functionalization time in our experiments.

Fig.2. Raman spectra of the CNT BPs with different reaction times with m-CPBA: (a) MWNT BP and (b) SWNT BP.

Mechanical properties

Figures 3 shows the tensile test curves and the mechanical properties of the pristine (not functionalized or control samples) long MWNT and SWNT buckypaper composites. The buckypaper weight fractions of the MWNT and SWNT composites were 42.7% and 40.7%, respectively. The tensile strength and tensile modulus of MWNT and SWNT nanocomposites are 560.5 MPa and 30.87 GPa, 478.9 MPa and 30 GPa respectively.

Fig.3. Mechanical properties of the pristine long CNT BP composites: (a) MWNT and (b) SWNT.

After functionalization, the mechanical properties of the MWNT and SWNT buckypaper composites noticeably improved are shown in Figure 4. Here, the nanotube weight fractions of the functionalized MWNT and SWNT buckypaper composites were 43.7% and 45.5%, respectively. The tensile modulus of the functionalized MWNT buckypaper composites improved by about 250%, and its tensile strength also improved. Especially, the strain-stress curves of the functionalized MWNT composites became almost straight lines, which mean that the tensile fracture process is an elastic and brittle fracture. There is no yielding stage for the functionalized buckypaper composites. The functionalized nanotubes were broken in the buckypaper composite samples, showing a brittle fracture mode and indicating better interfacial bonding and load transfer. In the process of functionalization, epoxy groups formed on the sidewalls of the nanotubes. The epoxy groups reacted with the curing agent to form covalent bonds during curing, as shown in Fig.5. Covalent bonds formed between the functionalized nanotubes and epoxy resin matrix, which resulted in a significant improvement of interfacial bonding and load transfers between the nanotubes and resin matrix. However, the tensile modulus improvement of the functionalized SWNT buckypapers composites was not as high as that of the MWNT composites. The tensile strength of the long SWNT buckypaper composites was decreased after the functionalization. The possible reason for reduced mechanical property enhancement of the functionalized SWNT buckypaper composites is that the perfect molecular structure of the SWNT was damaged by the functionalization. During functionalization, some sp² hybrid orbits were changed to sp³ hybrid orbits, resulting in the damage of the molecular perfection of the SWNTs, hence, a decrease in the mechanical properties [18]. This damage is especially critical for the SWNTs because SWNTs have only one layer wall. Any sp³ structures will weaken the sidewall structure on an SWNT, hence, leading to significant property degradation of the nanotubes after functionalization. On the other hand, the functionalization only damaged the outermost layer walls of the MWNTs. The functionalized MWNTs can possibly still hold most of their original mechanical properties after functionalization. Therefore, the enhancement of the modulus of the functionalized SWNT composites is much lower; its tensile strength was decreased due to possible SWNT property degradation. The typical stress-strain curves of SWNT and MWNT BP composites before and after functionalized are shown in Figure 6.

Fig.4. Mechanical properties of the functionalized long CNT BP composites: (a) MWNT and (b) SWNT.

Fig.5. Mechanism for improving interfacial bonding through covalent bonding between functionalized nanotubes and epoxy resin matrix.

Fig.6. Typical stress-strain curves of the SWNT and MWNT BP composites.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the fracture surfaces of the MWNT and SWNT BP composites. Improvements in interfacial bonding and nanotube breaks can be seen for

both functionalized MWNT and SWNT buckypaper composites. The functionalized MWNT buckypaper composites realized high mechanical performance comparable to carbon fiber fabric composites for structural applications.

Fig.7. SEM images of fracture surface s of the functionalized MWNT and SWNT BP composites, (a) Pristine MWNT BP composites, (b) Functionalized MWNT BP composites, (c) Pristine SWNT BP composites and (d) Functionalized SWNT BP composites.

Figure Captions should be centred and positioned below the figure.

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